

A Global Optimization Approach for Accurate Subgroup Parameters Generation

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ABSTRACT

The accurate calculation of subgroup parameters is crucial for the subgroup method of resonance self-shielding calculations. It still remains a key challenge. The traditional approaches suffer from limited accuracy and can even obtain unphysical results, such as negative subgroup cross sections. To address these limitations systematically, this paper introduces a multi-start global optimization strategy that automates this process by MATLAB's GlobalSearch solver. The subgroup parameters should be able to precisely reproduce the effective multi-group cross sections across a wide range of background conditions. It is essentially a constrained nonlinear global optimization problem. The primary advantage of this method is its systematic exploration of the parameter space, which effectively avoids local minima. And it eliminates unphysical subgroup parameters by adding constraints for subgroup parameters. The numerical results show that the subgroup parameters obtained by this method can accurately reproduce the effective multi-group cross sections, and the maximum relative error is mostly lower than 0.1%. Furthermore, it is in good agreement with the reference solution provided by the Monte Carlo reference program OpenMC for the critical calculation of HTGRs fuel elements. Compared to the traditional method, the present approach yields an improvement of approximately 50 pcm in the effective multiplication factor.

Keywords: resonance self-shielding calculation, subgroup method, subgroup parameters, GlobalSearch.

1. INTRODUCTION

In nuclear reactor physics, resonance self-shielding calculation is crucial to deterministic neutron calculations, as it produces problem-specific effective multi-group cross sections for subsequent transport and burnup analysis. Owing to its powerful geometric treatment, the subgroup method is implemented in many commercial codes like HELIOS [1], DECART [2], NECP-X [3], APOLLO3 [4] and ERANOS [5]. The key of the subgroup method is to further divide the multi-group into several subgroups based on the cross sections. Within each subgroup, by restricting the variation of the cross section, the range of flux variation is further limited, thereby achieving accurate description of resonance.

The subgroup method characterizes resonant nuclides using subgroup cross section and subgroup probability, referred to as subgroup parameters. The subgroup cross section is defined as the average value within the subgroup, determined under the condition of reaction rate conservation. The subgroup

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probability is the proportion of the subgroup energy range within the entire multi-group energy range. With these parameters, the subgroup fixed source equations can be constructed based on the specific problem. These equations are solved to obtain the subgroup fluxes using any transport calculation method [6], such as the method of characteristics (MOC). Finally, the effective multi-group cross sections are calculated by combining the subgroup parameters and subgroup fluxes.

The subgroup parameters directly affect the accuracy of the effective multi-group cross sections. The existing methods for calculating subgroup parameters include the moment method [7] and the fitting method [8]. In practice, the fitting method is generally preferred over the moment method, as the latter involves a computationally expensive and complex procedure for the moment. The fundamental principle of the fitting method is to reproduce the resonance cross section table, which is generated by accurately solving the neutron slowing-down equation.

In the fitting method, the Padé approximation method represents the most conventional approach [8]. This method selects a set of background cross section points and formulates a well-posed system of equations based on the relationship between the effective multi-group cross section and the subgroup parameters. However, since only a limited number of background cross sections are used, the accuracy of the resulting subgroup parameters cannot be guaranteed for conditions outside the selected points. Furthermore, the solutions may be physically inconsistent—for instance, yielding negative subgroup cross sections, which can cause the failure of solving the subgroup fixed source equation. To address this issue, codes like HELIOS [1] predefine the subgroup cross sections and then calculate the remaining parameters using the constrained least-squares method. However, the accuracy of subgroup parameters strongly depends on the predefined subgroup cross sections, which are typically tuned empirically and are specific to a particular multi-group cross section library. Consequently, there remains a clear need for a more robust and systematic approach to directly derive subgroup parameters from the multi-group cross section library, without relying on empirical prescriptions.

The calculation of subgroup parameters is essentially a constrained nonlinear global optimization problem. This paper presents a computational framework based on the GlobalSearch algorithm in MATLAB [9] to address this challenge. It is based on the scatter search mechanism [10] and automatically generates a large number of trial points within the feasible parameter space. For each promising trial point, it will calculate the local minima. A key advantage of the approach is to minimize redundant search efforts, thereby improving computational efficiency. The best solution among the obtained local minima is selected as the global optimum. This methodology enables highly accurate and universally applicable subgroup parameter generation. Furthermore, it readily accommodates physical constraints on parameter values, ensuring that results remain consistent with physical principles.

Section 2 provides the theoretical foundation of the subgroup method and the subgroup parameters calculation with GlobalSearch. Section 3 compares computational results to demonstrate the performance of the proposed approach. Finally, concluding remarks are given in Section 4.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL

2.1. The Subgroup Method

For an infinite homogeneous medium comprising a single resonant nuclide r and moderator nuclide m , the neutron energy spectrum can be derived under a set of approximations. These include neglecting

the fission source, ignoring up-scattering, and applying the intermediate resonance approximation. The flux is given by:

$$\phi(u) = \frac{\lambda_r \Sigma_{p,r} + \lambda_m \Sigma_{p,m}}{\Sigma_{t,r}(u) - (1 - \lambda_r) \Sigma_{s,r}(u) + \lambda_m \Sigma_{p,m}} = \frac{\lambda_r \sigma_{p,r} + \sigma_0}{\sigma_{int,r}(u) + \sigma_0} \quad (1)$$

where, ϕ is the neutron flux, Σ is the macroscopic cross section, λ is the intermediate resonance approximation factor, σ_p is the potential scattering cross section, $\sigma_{int} = \sigma_t - (1 - \lambda) \sigma_s$ is the intermediate resonance cross section, and $\sigma_0 = \lambda_m \Sigma_{p,m} / N_r$ is the dilution cross section.

In the subgroup method, a resonance group is divided into several subgroups by the magnitude of the cross sections. By introducing subgroup parameters, the effective multi-group cross section can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{x,g} = \frac{\int_{u_{g-1}}^{u_g} \sigma_x(u) \phi(u) du}{\int_{u_{g-1}}^{u_g} \phi(u) du} = \frac{\sum_n \sigma_{x,g,n} p_{g,n} \phi_{g,n}}{\sum_n p_{g,n} \phi_{g,n}} \quad (2)$$

where, x is the react type, g is the multi-group, n is the subgroup, u is the lethargy ($u = \ln(E_0/E)$), p is the subgroup probability.

Based on Eq. (1) and Eq. (2), the subgroup parameters of resonance nuclide can be calculated. The detailed calculation process is presented in the subsequent section. Then, the subgroup fixed source equation can be constructed based on the specific problem:

$$\vec{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \phi_{g,n}(\vec{r}) + \Sigma_{int,g,n}(\vec{r}) \phi_{g,n}(\vec{r}) = \lambda \Sigma_p(\vec{r}) \quad (3)$$

The subgroup flux can be obtained by solving this equation with any transport method. Then, the effective multi-group cross section is calculated based on Eq. (2).

2.2. The Calculation of Subgroup Parameters with GlobalSearch

The effective multi-group cross section represented by subgroup parameters is given by:

$$\sigma_{x,g} = \frac{\sum_n \sigma_{x,g,n} p_{g,n} \frac{\lambda_r \sigma_{p,r} + \sigma_0}{\sigma_{int,r,g,n} + \sigma_0}}{\sum_n p_{g,n} \frac{\lambda_r \sigma_{p,r} + \sigma_0}{\sigma_{int,r,g,n} + \sigma_0}} \quad (4)$$

For simplicity, in the subsequent derivations, group g and resonance nuclide r are omitted.

The resonance cross section table in the multi-group cross section library contains the effective multi-group cross sections σ_x^{table} corresponding to a series of background cross sections at different temperatures, obtained by solving the slowing-down equations precisely with the NJOY code [11]. Under different background cross section, the effective multi-group cross section calculated by subgroup parameters should be as close as possible to the value of the resonance cross section table. This problem can be described by the following expression:

$$\min_{\sigma_n, p_n} f(\sigma_n, p_n) = \min_{\sigma_n, p_n} \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\frac{\frac{\sum_n \frac{\sigma_{x,n} p_n}{\sigma_{int,n} + \sigma_{0,k}}}{p_n} - \sigma_{x,k}^{table}}{\sigma_{x,k}^{table}} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

where, k is the background cross section point.

Furthermore, the subgroup parameters must also satisfy the physical meaning. The subgroup cross section and subgroup probability are positive numbers. And the sum of the subgroup probabilities is 1. Therefore, this problem is essentially a constrained, highly nonlinear global optimization problem, as it involves coupled parameters in a rational function form.

To ensure that the result approaches the global optimum rather than a local minimum, a multi-start heuristic global optimization method was adopted. It integrates stochastic sampling, local search, and clustering strategies. Some trial points within the domain are generated by the scatter search algorithm [10]. A local optimization for a specific trial point is carried out to obtain the local optimum point. Each local optimum point corresponds to an attraction basin. This method evaluates the potential of each trial point and selectively performs local searches only for promising candidates, thereby reducing redundant computations within the same attraction basin. Finally, by comparing the known local optimal solutions, the global optimal solution is selected, which are the subgroup parameters.

The global optimization of subgroup parameters was carried out using the GlobalSearch algorithm provided in MATLAB's Global Optimization Toolbox [9]. In this paper, the computational workflow was re-engineered to interface directly with the multi-group cross section library's data structures, and the solver parameters were meticulously configured to enhance convergence. This established a robust and automated global optimization procedure tailored for the subgroup parameters calculation.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Calculation Accuracy of Subgroup Parameters

This paper compares the traditional Padé approximation method [8] and the proposed GlobalSearch-based approach for calculating subgroup parameters. And the HDF5-formatted multi-group cross section library XPZLIB [12] with the WIMS-69 energy group structure [13] is used. The resonance energy range spans from 4 eV to 9118 eV, covering 13 resonance groups.

The traditional method requires the combination of background section points. To ensure the best possible accuracy under this framework, an enumeration strategy that evaluates all feasible combinations of background cross-sections was adopted. This approach is referred to as the enumeration method. In XPZLIB, the number of background section points is set to 20 (excluding infinite dilution). The maximum number of subgroups is set to 8 for both methods.

To evaluate the accuracy of both approaches, ^{238}U was analyzed, a representative resonance nuclide in reactors, such as high temperature gas cooled reactors (HTGRs). Figure 1 shows the fitting error of the effective multi-group cross section of ^{238}U in the 25th group (15.97 ~ 27.7 eV).

Figure 1. The fitting error of ^{238}U in the 25th group.

The fitting error is defined as the relative error between the effective multi-group cross section calculated from the subgroup parameters and the reference value in the resonance cross section table. As shown in the figure, the accuracy of enumeration method exhibits a strong dependence on the background cross section. Since this method utilizes only a subset of the background cross sections available in the reference table, it achieves high precision exclusively at the selected points, while considerable errors arise elsewhere. Conversely, the GlobalSearch method shows consistently high accuracy across the entire range of background cross-sections.

Figure 2. The comparison of fitting accuracy of XPZLIB.

Figure 2 compares the distribution of fitting errors for all subgroup parameters in the XPZLIB, calculated using the two methods. The fitting error, defined by the following equation, is plotted on the horizontal axis against the number of resonance groups on the vertical axis.

$$\varepsilon = \max_{\substack{k=1,\dots,K \\ x=int,tot,scat\dots}} \left| \frac{\frac{\sum_n \frac{\sigma_{x,n} p_n}{\sigma_{int,n} + \sigma_{0,k}}}{\sum_n \frac{p_n}{\sigma_{int,n} + \sigma_{0,k}}} - \sigma_{x,k}^{table}}{\sigma_{x,k}^{table}} \right| \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

As shown in the figure, the GlobalSearch method achieves a substantial improvement in the accuracy of subgroup parameters. The proportion of resonance energy groups with a fitting error below 0.1% increased from 19.2% to 97.9%. This level of precision establishes a highly reliable framework for the subgroup resonance calculation method.

3.2. Subgroup Resonance Calculations for HTGRs Fuel Element

XPZ is a lattice physics calculation program for HTGRs [14]. In this study, two versions of the multi-group cross section library—embedded with subgroup parameters obtained different calculation method—were used in XPZ to perform criticality calculations. Numerical verification was carried out on three representative fuel elements. Table I summarizes the basic descriptions of these cases. The specific geometric and material parameters of fuel elements can be found in Ref. [12]. Bondarenko iteration method [15] was used to deal with the resonance interference effect. The generalized Hébert model [16] was adopted to treat double heterogeneity effect. The white boundary condition is adopted in all cases.

Table I. Summary of three validation cases

Description	Fuel Enrichment (%)	Packing ratio (%)
HTR-PM fuel element	8.5	7
HTR-PM fuel element	4.25	7
HTR-10 fuel element	17	5

The Monte Carlo program OpenMC [17] is used to provide the reference solution. The OpenMC simulations were configured with the following parameters: 1000 total generations (including 100 inactive generations) and 100,000 particles per generation.

A comparison of the criticality calculation results using the two versions of subgroup parameters is presented in Table II. The GlobalSearch method is shown to achieve a superior accuracy in the effective multiplication factor compared to the enumeration method.

Table II. The critical results for different subgroup parameters

Case	OpenMC	Difference from Enumeration method (pcm)	Difference from GlobalSearch method (pcm)
HTR-PM fuel element	1.56099	87	-10

HTR-PM fuel element	1.43570	58	-19
HTR-10 fuel element	1.68248	77	-55

Figure 3 shows the macroscopic reaction rates in HTR-PM fuel element (8.5 wt%). The GlobalSearch method demonstrates superior accuracy across resonance energy groups, thus providing more precise critical results.

Figure 3. The comparison of macro reaction rates in HTR-PM fuel element (8.5 wt%).

4. CONCLUSIONS

Accurately determining subgroup parameters is a key challenge in subgroup resonance self-shielding method. To address this issue, this paper introduces a multi-start global optimization strategy implemented using MATLAB's GlobalSearch algorithm. The proposed method achieves significantly higher accuracy than conventional approaches, with 98% of the subgroup parameters fitted to errors below 0.1%. It also effectively eliminates non-physical results, such as negative subgroup cross sections through the direct imposition of constraints. This robust approach requires no empirical parameter estimation and is readily applicable to various multi-group cross section libraries. Resonance calculations performed with the resulting parameters show excellent agreement with OpenMC reference solutions, and criticality calculations yield more accurate effective multiplication factors compared to those from traditional methods.

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